

Sidorov Denys*specialist degree, Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University***Abstract**

The article analyzes mobile optimization strategies in frontend development aimed at enhancing the performance and usability of mobile applications. It examines architectural approaches such as modular and microservices structures, as well as rendering methods (server-side and client-side) and their impact on load speed and interface responsiveness. Special attention is given to application state management methods, responsive design, and adherence to accessibility standards, which together improve the user experience for a wide audience.

Keywords: mobile optimization, frontend development, architecture, rendering, accessibility, performance.

Introduction

With the rise in popularity of mobile devices (MD) and increasing demands for speed and responsiveness in applications, optimizing the frontend architecture for mobile platforms has become one of the key tasks in web development. In an environment of high traffic and limited resources on MD, factors such as performance and accessibility are critically important for ensuring a positive user experience (UX) and the competitiveness of a product in the market.

However, optimizing frontend applications for MD faces a number of unique challenges, including low network bandwidth, limited computing resources, and the high susceptibility of mobile users to unpredictable network conditions. Traditional web development approaches focused on desktop devices often fail to perform adequately in a mobile environment, necessitating new architectural solutions and optimization strategies.

The aim of this work is to investigate architectural approaches such as modularity and microservices architecture, as well as to study the application of rendering technologies like Server-Side Rendering (SSR) and Client-Side Rendering (CSR) in high-load mobile applications. It is hypothesized that a combination of architectural and technological strategies will achieve high performance and provide a high level of accessibility.

Main part. Analysis of architectural approaches in high-load mobile applications

One of the key aspects of effective mobile optimization is the **proper choice of architecture** for the frontend application, which is especially relevant for high-load applications. Modern approaches in mobile frontend development offer two main architectural strategies: modular and microservices architectures.

Modular architecture allows an application to be divided into independent components, simplifying maintenance and improving loading speed due to the possibility of parallel rendering of various modules. This architecture also provides the ability for selective loading of necessary resources, which is especially important under mobile constraints [1].

On the other hand, **microservices architecture** implies the division of an application into small independent services that can be deployed and updated independently of each other. This allows for flexible load management and improves response time, as each service operates autonomously, reducing the overall

amount of data transferred to the device. The combination of modular and microservices architectures in high-load applications enables faster loading and minimizes the volume of data transmitted over the network. This is particularly important for MD, as limited resources require more efficient load distribution. The microservices approach allows for the application of various strategies to optimize interface rendering and resource allocation, particularly when using **SSR** and **CSR** [2, 3].

The SSR method offers rendering of the application on the **server-side** before sending the page to the client device. When accessing the application, the server processes the request and returns a fully formed HTML page with complete content, which is displayed on the user's screen. This approach allows users to see fully loaded content faster, as the main data processing is performed by the server, reducing the load on the mobile device.

However, SSR also has its drawbacks. The primary disadvantage is the increased load on the server, as each new request requires separate page generation. In high-load applications, this can lead to increased server response times and reduced overall system performance. To circumvent this limitation, hybrid approaches are sometimes used, such as pre-rendering frequently visited pages, which reduces the need for SSR for every request.

In contrast, the **CSR method** assumes that content rendering occurs directly on the client-side. In this case, the server sends a minimal HTML structure with the necessary script links, while all content rendering is performed by the browser after receiving and executing JavaScript. In CSR applications, data is dynamically loaded and processed on the client side, ensuring a smoother transition between pages and enhancing the interactivity of the application [4].

However, CSR also has its drawbacks. One of the main disadvantages is the time to interactive (TTI), which increases as time is required to load and execute JavaScript on the client. This can lead users to see a blank screen or partially loaded content until all necessary scripts have finished loading, which degrades the UX. CSR is also less effective for Search Engine Optimization (SEO), as search engine crawlers may not wait for the full loading of JavaScript to index content, potentially reducing the visibility of the application in search engines.

The choice between SSR and CSR depends on the application's tasks and the target audience's preferences. A combined approach known as **hybrid rendering** allows for leveraging the advantages of both strategies. For instance, SSR can be used for the initial page rendering (which improves loading time and SEO), while CSR can be used for loading and updating subsequent interface elements, enhancing interactivity.

In addition to hybrid rendering, there are many other strategies for optimizing the performance of mobile applications. The main ones include **codesplitting**, **asynchronous resource loading**, and **graphics optimization** [5]. These methods aim to minimize loading time and improve interface performance.

One popular strategy for mobile optimization is **code splitting**, which allows for loading only the modules necessary at a particular stage of application use. For example, for the main screen, only the core functionality can be loaded, while additional modules are asynchronously loaded as needed. This approach helps significantly reduce the initial loading time, positively impacting the UX.

Asynchronous loading also allows for optimizing resource loading and avoiding blocking the main thread, which is particularly important for heavy applications with high load. Asynchronous server requests are performed in parallel with the main application processes, helping to reduce the TTI and improve interface responsiveness.

To improve performance in mobile applications, it is important to optimize graphic resources. This includes images, videos, and other multimedia data, which account for a significant share of the total volume of downloaded data. The use of modern image formats such as WebP allows for a reduction in file sizes and faster loading. WebP provides improved compression compared to JPEG and PNG without significant loss of quality.

Another effective technique is **lazy loading**. This technique allows for loading images and other resources only when they actually come into the user's view. This helps conserve resources and improve performance by avoiding the excessive loading of data that may not be needed during user interaction with the application.

Improving responsiveness and optimizing UI in UX

Responsive design is an integral part of mobile optimization, as MD vary in screen sizes, resolutions, and orientations. Responsive design entails adapting the interface to various resolutions and pixel densities, ensuring usability on MD. It is important that the interface elements remain easy to navigate and interact with on any device [6]. Responsive design is particularly relevant in the context of the growing usage of MD. According to statistics for 2024, MD account for approximately 55% of internet traffic, with a full traffic change schedule presented in picture 1.

Pic. 1. Percentage of mobile device website traffic worldwide [7]

Application state management is a crucial aspect of mobile optimization. To maintain high performance, many developers use approaches such as **centralized state storage**, for example, **Redux** or **MobX** [8].

Redux is based on the principle of a **single source of truth**, where all application state is stored in a single state object (**store**). This state can only be modified by **dispatching actions**, which are handled by **reducers**. In Redux, data flows in one direction, simplifying the understanding of data flows and debugging. When the state is updated, components that depend on this state are automatically re-rendered. This approach is suitable for **large applications** with complex architecture, where state management requires explicit control and debugging.

In contrast, **MobX** uses a **reactive approach** to state management. It focuses on automatically updating components when data changes, without the need to explicitly dispatch actions or update the state. MobX employs an observer mechanism that automatically responds to state changes. This method is suitable for **small and medium applications** where fast and simple state management is required without a lot of configuration and **boilerplate code** (pre-written code or templates that can be used as a basis for creating new applications or components). Centralized state storage allows for managing state on the **client side** and minimizes the number of server requests, reducing network load and speeding up interactions.

The process of load testing and subsequent optimization of the mobile application is conducted with a focus on evaluating its performance under

various conditions. Key performance metrics, essential for assessing the application's efficiency and responsiveness, are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Key performance metrics [9]		
Metric	Description	Target value
Time to First Byte (TTFB)	Time until the first byte is received from the server.	< 200 ms
First Contentful Paint (FCP)	Time until the first content is rendered on the screen.	< 1 s
Largest Contentful Paint (LCP)	Time until the largest content element is loaded.	< 2.5 s
Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS)	Measures the visual stability of content on the screen.	< 0.1 s
Time to Interactive (TTI)	Time required for the page to become fully interactive.	< 5 s

The metrics in Table 1 provide a foundational basis for evaluating and enhancing the mobile application's performance and responsiveness. By aligning with these target values, the application can achieve faster load times, improved visual stability, and a smoother user experience. These benchmarks are instrumental in guiding the optimization process, ensuring the application meets the necessary standards for efficiency and user satisfaction under varying load conditions.

Performance and accessibility optimization is essential for developing interfaces that are both responsive and user-friendly, ensuring access to a broad and diverse audience. Optimizing performance metrics, such as load times and interactivity, has a direct impact on user experience, particularly for those on slower networks or using older devices. By reducing loading delays and improving content stability, developers can minimize user frustration and increase engagement. Additionally, optimized performance reduces resource consumption, which benefits both users and the environment by lowering data usage and energy demands.

Accessibility optimization complements performance improvements by supporting a wide range of users, including those with disabilities. This involves incorporating features such as screen reader compatibility, keyboard navigation, and adequate color contrast to make interfaces usable for individuals with various needs. Accessibility efforts go beyond regulatory compliance, reflecting a commitment to inclusive digital experiences.

Conclusion

Optimizing frontend architecture for mobile applications is essential in today's digital landscape, characterized by diverse device capabilities and user expectations. Employing architectural strategies like modular and microservices architectures, along with rendering techniques such as SSR and CSR, can significantly enhance performance and UX.

Additionally, integrating performance optimization strategies, responsive design, and accessibility standards fosters inclusivity and improves user engagement. As mobile internet traffic continues to rise, these

approaches will be critical for developers aiming to create high-performing, responsive, and accessible mobile applications that meet the demands of a dynamic user base.

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